

Studies in the Synthesis of Quinoline Derivatives : Part IV* : Synthesis of Furoquinolines

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2-Methyl-3-formyl-4-quinolinol (Ia) on condensation with ethyl bromoacetate gave (IIa), but on hydrolysis original quinoline derivative was obtained back. (Ia) on condensation with ethyl bromomalonate gave 4-methyl-2-carboethoxymethoxy quinoline (IVa), which on hydrolysis and subsequent decarboxylation furnished 4-methyl-furo(3,2-c)quinoline (IVc). Similar condensation of 2,8-dimethyl-3-formyl-4-quinolinol (Ib) and 6-methoxy-2-methyl-3-formyl-4-quinolinol (Ic) with ethyl bromomalonate gave (IVd) and (IVe) respectively.

Furoquinolines have received considerable importance as they not only occur in nature but also possess therapeutic properties. On reviewing the literature it has been found that all naturally occurring furoquinolines have no substituent in the furan ring and that they are usually synthesised from dihydrofuroquinolines by making use of bromination-dehydrobromination technique^{1,2}. The alternative method³ makes the use of building up of the α -pyrone ring on *o*-hydroxyaldehydoquinoline derivatives or Pechmann reaction on 4-hydroxyquinoline derivatives followed by bromination and subsequent ring contraction by alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution.

The present work was undertaken to synthesise furo (3,2-c)quinoline derivatives, having no substituent in the furan ring starting from 4-hydroxy-3-formyl-2-methylquinoline (Ia) derivatives. (Ia) was condensed with ethyl bromoacetate by refluxing them in ethyl methyl ketone in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate to give 2-methyl-3-formyl-4-carboethoxymethoxyquinoline (IIa). This on hydrolysis with potassium hydroxide solution did not give the corresponding acid (III) but only 2-methyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxyquinoline was obtained back. An attempt to cyclise (IIa) to furo (3,2-c) quinoline derivative by heating with fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride also met with failure. Similar

- I a, $R_1 = R_2 = H$
 b, $R_1 = H; R_2 = CH_3$
 c, $R_1 = OCH_3; R_2 = H$

- II a, $R_1 = R_2 = H$
 b, $R_1 = H; R_2 = CH_3$

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1. M. F. Grundon and N. J. McCorkindale, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 2177.
2. R. G. Cooke and H. F. Hynes, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1958, **11**, 225.
3. Y. Asahina and M. Inubuse, *Ber.*, 1932, **65**, 61.

condensation of 2,8-dimethyl-3-formyl-4-quinolinol (Ib) with ethyl bromoacetate gave the corresponding 4-carboethoxy methoxyderivative (IIb) which when hydrolysed gave the original quinoline derivative (Ib) back.

- IV a, $R_1 = R_2 = H$; $R_3 = COOC_2H_5$
 b, $R_1 = R_2 = H$; $R_3 = COOH$
 c, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$
 d, $R_1 = R_3 = H$; $R_2 = CH_3$
 e, $R_1 = OCH_3$; $R_2 = R_3 = H$

In view of the failure of this method in the 4-hydroxyquinoline series, the method developed by Tanaka⁴ to build up unsubstituted furan ring by making use of ethyl bromomalonate was next tried. When 2-methyl-3-formyl-4-quinolinol was condensed with ethyl bromomalonate in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in refluxing ethyl methylketone, it gave 4-methyl-2-carboethoxyfuro(3,2-c)quinoline (IVa). This on hydrolysis afforded 4-methyl-furo(3,2-c)quinoline-2-carboxylic acid (IVb) which underwent decarboxylation to 4-methyl-furo(3,2-c)quinoline (IVc) when heated with copper bronze.

2,8-Dimethyl-4-quinolinol and 6-methoxy-2-methyl-4-quinolinol when subjected to Reimer-Tiemann reaction with chloroform and alkali, they gave the corresponding 3-formyl derivatives (Ib and c). These on similar condensation with ethyl bromomalonate followed by hydrolysis and decarboxylation gave 4,6-dimethyl-furo(3,2-c)quinoline (IVd) and 8-methoxy-2-methyl-furo(3,2-c)quinoline (IVe) respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation of 2-methyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxyquinoline with ethyl bromoacetate: 2-Methyl-3-formyl-4-carboethoxymethoxyquinoline (IIa): 2-Methyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxyquinoline (1.8 g.) was dissolved in ethyl methyl ketone (100 ml.) and refluxed with ethyl bromoacetate (1.6 g.) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g.) for 12 hrs on a steam bath. The ethyl methyl ketone was removed and the reaction mixture was added to water. The product which separated crystallised from benzene, m.p. 189°. (Found: C, 65.80; H, 5.45; N, 5.60. $C_{15}H_{15}O_4N$ requires C, 65.92; H, 5.53; N, 5.13%).

Hydrolysis: The above 4-carboethoxymethoxyquinoline derivative (1 g.) was mixed with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml; 10%) and left overnight. The resulting solution was neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid and the product which separated crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 273°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 2-methyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxyquinoline was not depressed.

4. S. Tanaka, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 872.

2,8-Dimethyl-3-formyl-4-quinolinol (Ib) : 2,8-Dimethyl-4-quinolinol (5 g.) was mixed with sodium hydroxide solution (50 ml.; 25%) and chloroform (10 ml.). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 10 hr. After removing excess of chloroform it was diluted with water and filtered. The clear filtrate on acidification with glacial acetic acid gave the product which was filtered and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 258°. Yield 1.5 g. (Found : C, 71.96; H, 5.58; N, 6.95. $C_{12}H_{11}O_2N$ requires C, 71.062; H, 5.51; N, 6.96%).

It gave 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone on adding clear solution of formyl derivative in glacial acetic acid to the solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in glacial acetic acid. The product crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 310°. (Found : N, 17.95. $C_{18}H_{15}O_5N_5$ requires N, 18.37%).

2,8-Dimethyl-3-formyl-4-carboethoxymethoxyquinoline (IIb) : 2,8-Dimethyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxyquinoline (2.8 g.) was dissolved in ethyl methyl ketone (200 ml.) and refluxed with anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g.) and ethyl bromo acetate (1.6 g.) on a steam bath for 12 hr. On working up as before the product crystallised from benzene, m.p. 108°. (Found : C, 67.11; H, 5.99; N, 4.83. $C_{16}H_{17}O_4N$ requires C, 66.88; H, 5.96; N, 4.88%).

Hydrolysis : The above 4-carboethoxymethoxyquinoline derivative (1 g.) was mixed with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml.; 10%) and left overnight. On working up as before the product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 258°. Mixed m.p. with 2,8-dimethyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxyquinoline obtained as described earlier was 258°.

Condensation of 2-methyl-3-formyl-4-quinolinol with ethyl bromomalonate : 4-Methyl-2-carboethoxyfuro(3,2-c)quinoline (IVa) : 2-Methyl-3-formyl-4-quinolinol (3.7 g.) was dissolved in ethyl methyl ketone (200 ml.) and refluxed with ethyl bromomalonate (4.8 g.) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (10 g.) on a steam bath for 35 hr. The ethyl methyl ketone was removed and the reaction mixture was added to water. The product which separated crystallised from benzenepetroleum ether mixture, m.p. 115°. Yield 2 g. (Found : C, 70.21; H, 4.87; N, 5.31. $C_{15}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 70.58; H, 5.13; N, 5.49%).

IR Spectrum (nujol) showed a strong ester, carbonyl band at 1730 cm^{-1} .

4-Methyl-furo (3,2-c) quinoline-2-carboxylic acid (IVb) : The above ester (1 g.) was treated with alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution (20 ml.; 10%) and left overnight. The resulting solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid (50%). On cooling in refrigerator the product which separated crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 280°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found : C, 68.55; H, 3.55; N, 5.78. $C_{13}H_9O_3N$ requires C, 68.72; H, 3.99; N, 6.17%).

Decarboxylation of 4-methyl-furo (3,2-c) quinoline-2-carboxylic acid : 4-Methyl-furo (3,2-c) quinoline (IVc) : The above acid (0.5 g.) was mixed with copper bronze (1 g.) and heated in an oil bath above its m.p. (280°) with vacuum till the effervescence ceased (10 min.). After cooling the product was extracted with benzene. On evaporation of the solvent the product obtained crystallised from ether petroleum, m.p. 89°. (Found : C, 78.87; H, 4.81; N, 7.41. $C_{12}H_9ON$ requires C, 78.67; H, 4.95; N, 7.65%).

4,6-Dimethyl-2-carboethoxyfuro (3,2-c) quinoline : The 2,8-Dimethyl-3-formyl-4-quinolinol (3 g.) was refluxed in ethyl methyl ketone (250 ml.) with anhydrous potassium carbonate

(7 g.) and ethyl bromo malonate (3.6 g.) on a steam bath for 35 hr. On working up as before the product crystallised from benzene petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 128°. (Found : C, 71.33; H, 5.22; N, 5.28. $C_{16}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 71.36; H, 5.61; N, 5.20%).

4,6-Dimethylfuro (3,2-c) quinoline-2-carboxylic acid : The above ester (1 g.) was treated with alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution (20 ml.; 10%) and left overnight. On working up as before the product crystallised from dil. alcohol, m.p. 248°. (Found : C, 69.58; H, 4.22; N, 5.69. $C_{14}H_{11}O_3N$ requires C, 69.70; H, 4.59; N, 5.80%).

4,6-Dimethylfuro (3,2-c) quinoline (IVd) : The above acid (0.5 g.) was mixed with copper bronze (1 g.) and heated in an oil bath above its m.p. (248°) with vacuum till the effervescence ceased (10 min.). On working up as before the product crystallised from ether petroleum, m.p. 128°. (Found : C, 79.32; H, 5.76; N, 6.99. $C_{13}H_{11}ON$ requires C, 79.16; H, 5.62; N, 7.10%).

6-Methoxy-2-methyl-3-formyl-4-quinolinol (Ic) : 6-Methoxy-2-methyl-4-quinolinol (5 g.) was subjected to Reimer-Tiemann reaction with sodium hydroxide solution (50 ml.; 25%) and chloroform (10 ml.). It was refluxed on a water bath for 10 hr. On working up as before the product crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 290°. (Found : C, 66.18; H, 5.20; N, 6.71. $C_{12}H_{11}O_3N$ requires C, 66.35; H, 5.10; N, 6.45%).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was prepared as usual and crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 320°. (Found : N, 17.43. $C_{18}H_{15}O_6N_5$ requires N, 17.63%).

8-Methoxy-4-methyl-2-carboethoxy-furo (3,2-c) quinoline : The above 3-formyl derivative (2.2 g.) was refluxed in ethyl methyl ketone (300 ml.) with anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g.) and ethyl bromomalonate (2.4 g.) on a steam bath for 35 hr. On working up as before the product crystallised from benzene (charcoal), m.p. 182°. (Found : C, 67.19; H, 5.11; N, 4.85. $C_{16}H_{15}O_4N$ requires C, 67.36; H, 5.30; N, 4.91%).

IR spectrum (nujol) showed a strong ester carbonyl band at 1730 cm^{-1} .

8-Methoxy-4-methyl-furo (3,2-c) quinoline-2-carboxylic acid : The above ester (1 g.) was treated with alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution (20 ml.; 10%) and left overnight. On working up as before the acid crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 277°. (Found : C, 65.22; H, 4.10; N, 5.00. $C_{14}O_{11}O_4N$ requires C, 65.36; H, 4.31; N, 5.45%).

8-Methoxy-4-methyl-furo (3,2-c) quinoline (IVe) : The above acid (0.5 g.) was mixed with copper bronze (1 g.) and heated in an oil bath above its m.p. (277°) with vacuum till the effervescence ceased (10 min.). On working up as before the product crystallised from ether petroleum, m.p. 81°. (Found : C, 73.07; H, 4.88; N, 6.43. $C_{13}H_{11}O_2N$ requires C, 73.22; H, 5.20; N, 6.57%).

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